

Existential sociolinguistics and existential justice: Addressing minority-language issues in multilingual societies

David BALOSA, The School District of Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, United States

This study explores the way an existential sociolinguistic paradigm helps to deconstruct the oppression and exclusion of minority or indigenous languages in multilingual societies in the Global North and in the Global South. It uses the theoretical framework of existential sociolinguistics and the method of philosophical reflection to address the question: How can existential sociolinguistics foster existential justice in *building more humane relations* (BMHR) among languages within multilingual societies? It argues that existential justice as an overarching justice encompasses all models of justice and should help promote an attitude of *linguistic intercultural solidarity* and a treatment of dignity towards all languages. This study concludes that laws and policies about languages in modern multilingual societies need to overcome *econotechnocracy*, that is, a world order in which economic and technological powers subordinate justice, democracy, and the legitimacy of less-powerful nations, cultures, and languages. This suggests that all existing languages deserve dignifying treatment.

Keywords: Econotechnocracy; Existential Justice; Existential Sociolinguistics; Linguistic Intercultural Solidarity; Multilingual Societies

1. Introduction

The problem that this study points out is that minority languages in multilingual societies are discriminated against in the Global North and in the Global South. The local, national, and international political-economic and educational landscape is dominated by few local, regional, or international languages which are the dominant local, national, and international languages to the detriment of minority or indigenous languages which are rural languages and languages of indigenous and “vulnerable people” (Hornberger, 2011, p. 1). The purpose of this study is to propose a new mindset with respect to the way in which multilingual societies in the Global North and in the Global South plan and regulate the use of languages in local, national, and international political and educational spaces. I propose the mindset of existential justice for *building more humane relationships* (BMHR) and cultivating equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity (cf. Chaka, 2024; Mapuya, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Ndlangamandla et al., 2024; Xu & Fang, 2024).¹ In this regard, Hult (2023)

reminds us that communication is fundamentally a relational phenomenon and that through communication human beings create relationships that frame the way we perceive and relate to the world and each other. From this perspective, discrimination against minority languages is a relational discrimination in that this discrimination excludes or marginalises minority languages and the speakers of these languages. The consequences of this discrimination affect the rights of all human beings and communities to participate in the prospect of sustainable development (Hult, 2023; Tonkin, 2023).

To transform this mindset critically and radically to more inclusive and sensitive “attitudes, emotions, and actions” or a mindset of existential justice, we need theoretical frameworks and research methods that encourage equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity” (Balosa, 2022a, pp. 148, 155; Dworkin, 1978; Rawls, 2001). To respond to this study’s research question—how existential sociolinguistics can foster existential justice in *building more humane relationships* (BMHR) among languages and communities within multilingual societies—I employ the theoretical framework of existential sociolinguistics and the research method of philosophical reflection. I argue that all languages, independently of their political-economic, sociocultural, technological, and geographical power, are national and universal cultural resources, deserve equitable treatment and use in national and international affairs (Coulmas, 2018; Edwards, 2012; Rösen, 2021); That is, any discrimination against minority or indigenous languages is problematic because it does not merely affect the dignity and the rights of these languages and their speakers, but it also affects the nature of justice and democracy professed by local, national, and international laws. The following sections in this study will explain how this understanding can contribute to a critical radical transformation of the present engrained oppression of minority languages into justice among all languages and all speech communities. In conclusion, I propose that through existential justice, multilingual societies should understand that language issues are relational issues and that addressing them equitably promotes unity within diversity and dignity for all (Fishman, 1976, 1989).

2. Background

2.1. Existential sociolinguistics in fostering existential justice

The background of this study derived from the research question: How can existential sociolinguistics foster existential justice in *building more humane relations* among languages and communities within multilingual societies? The majority of laws and policies related to language issues in multilingual societies seem to merely promote language use for business and market purposes rather than establishing and developing *linguistic intercultural solidarity* among all

languages. By linguistic intercultural solidarity I refer to a treatment of equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity for all languages including languages in the position of power or control in the context of multilingual speech community (Fishman, 1989; Nagel, 1978). Therefore, looking at existential sociolinguistics as a paradigm and a theoretical and practical interdisciplinary subfield of sociolinguistics may guide us in discovering strategies towards more humane language policies (Balosa, 2022a; 2022c). In addition, as a philosophical sociolinguistic paradigm, existential sociolinguistics fosters existential justice by providing an overarching framework of justice and making existential justice a macro justice for human rights, human dignity, sociopolitical rights, and sustainable development for all.

The fact that existential justice encompasses all models of justice should encourage national and international laws in using its framework to overcome the ambivalent attitude toward minority languages and promote *linguistic intercultural solidarity* in the use of languages in multilingual societies. It is important to ask this question in the current world of multiple agendas and visible inequalities if we are to foster equitable and dignifying cultural and linguistic relations (Grusky & Hill, 2018). This implies that scholars should be encouraged to look at appropriate approaches or theories to inform legislations and policies related to language issues in multilingual societies for the common good.

2.2. Existential sociolinguistics as a theoretical framework

This study employs existential sociolinguistics as its theoretical and practical framework. Since meaning is often injected into any utterance from outside (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2022), it is vital to define what is meant by 'existential sociolinguistics' here. Balosa (2022a, pp. 148, 155) defines 'existential sociolinguistics' as:

... a branch of sociolinguistics that draws its insights from sociopolitical, anthropological, legal, philosophical, economic, historical, and psychological approaches to substantiate the idea of the inseparability of the treatment of languages from the treatment of their speakers or their speech communities.

Hence, any mistreatment or oppression of a language, consciously or unconsciously, like in the case of an exclusion of certain languages in political or educational policies in favour of dominant local, national or international languages is tantamount to an oppression toward the speakers of these languages. This discrimination contributes to the individual and communal degradation of conditions of life and the violation of the sociocultural, political-economic, and legal rights of indigenous people and their communities. It

especially destroys the opportunity for cooperation between people from speech communities and intercultural experiences within multilingual and multicultural societies. This definition is in harmony with Piller (2016) who argues that “the way we speak is an integral part of who we are” (p. 4). It is also in harmony with Williams (1977) who claims that “[a] definition of language is always, implicitly or explicitly, a definition of human beings in the world” (p. 21). Williams (1977, p. 21) adds that:

[t]he received major categories—‘world’, ‘reality’, ‘nature’, ‘human’—may be related to the category ‘language’, but it is now commonplace to observe that all categories, including the category ‘language’, are themselves constructions in language, and can thus only with effort, and within a particular system of thought, be separated from language for relational inquiry.”

If this perception is seriously considered, all languages, including minority languages must receive equitable treatment and dignity since they are the definition of human beings in different territories of the world.

Since the colonial era, the Global North and the Global South have theoretically and practically treated minority or indigenous languages with disparagement, humiliation, and with discriminatory attitudes and policies. This mindset has not built trust, transparent cooperation, and mutual-respect relationships; on the contrary, it has engendered alienation and contentious politics and relations across multilingual societies (Tilly, 2005; Tilly & Tarrow, 2015; Wa Thiong’o, 1986). While general sociolinguistics focusses on language use, linguistic survival and death, role, and relationships among languages (Danesi, 2020; Edwards, 2013), existential sociolinguistics emphasises the recognition, the regulation, and the use of all languages by the fact of their existence, whether they hold some sociocultural, political-economic, moral/religious, technological, and geographical power. Therefore, existential sociolinguistics argues that we need existential justice to address inequalities and oppression if we are serious about equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity (Grusky & Hill, 2018; Piller, 2016; Rösen & Laass, 2009). In a world where most people are not Western, existential justice should be the most comprehensive model of justice to address issues related to social justice and other justices if we are to take all people’s rights seriously (Dworkin, 1978; Rawls, 1979).

Existential sociolinguistics as a paradigm in dealing with languages and intercultural relations fosters “global intercultural solidarity” toward a sustainable development for all (Balosa, 2022c, p. 16). Needless to say, it also counteracts *econotechnocracy* and its world order by proposing its five principles: (1) Human dignity, (2) global intercultural citizenship, (3) the political legitimacy of linguistic minority rights, (4) existential literacy, and (5)

national language policy (Balosa, 2022a, p. 155). This suggests that using this theoretical framework provides a potential set of strategies in addressing not merely linguistic injustice and oppression but also in addressing discriminatory ideologies and politics that degrade our common humanity today (Marcel, 1954; 1963). For example, empowering rural areas' languages of the Global South is an important policy in empowering rural communities and their languages to participate in local, national and international "networks" and sustainable development project (Tilly & Tilly, 1998).

2.3. Language as an embedded existential reality of life

Existential sociolinguistics emphasises the treatment of a language as an *embedded existential reality of life* as well as race, gender, age, rurality, and urbanity. Therefore, any linguistic, racial, gender, and environmental discriminatory attitude, emotion, and action is tantamount to *an existential discriminatory behaviour*. This practice is counterproductive to *building more humane relationships* (BMHR) and destructive to "humanity, order, unity, security, equity" (Balosa, 2022b, p. 7296). This behaviour prevents minority languages and their speakers from flourishing at their full moral, sociocultural, political-economic, environmental, and technological natural capabilities and "well-being and advantage" (Sen, 1999, pp. 3, 4). For example, discussing work under capitalism, Tilly and Tilly (1998, p. 76) argue that:

. . . all work contracts involve setting limits to the time, place, quality, quantity of effort and/or product involved, trust, difference in their presumptions of previous training, knowledge of the local scene, outside connections and many other features of the parties' characteristics and performances.

They concluded that work "contracts definitely cover transactions involving relationships and arrangement just as long as those arrangements involve human effort, production or transfer of use value, and durable, mutual recognition of rights, obligations, and limits" (Tilly & Tilly, 1998, p. 76.).

This understanding is critically important in the analysis of the need for equitable language policies in favor of all languages if the well-being and flourishing of all languages and their speech communities are to contribute to the global intercultural well-being of and relational trust in our modern world (Blackledge & Creese, 2010; Guilherme, 2002; MacNeil, 2020; Tilly, 2005; Phipps & Guilherme, 2004). Languages, like all existing species, need to be equitably and inclusively identified to reflect the authentic sociolinguistic identity of our linguistic universe. In this regard, American linguist Stephen R. Anderson (2012) argues: "In fact, the task of identifying (and then counting) the world's languages is strikingly similar to that of identifying (and counting)

the world's biological species" (Anderson, 2012, p. 3). This statement epitomizes the significance of an existential sociolinguistic approach in the treatment of linguistic diversity in multilingual societies. That is, the same trust and confidence we have in counting and respecting biologic species, the same trust and confidence should also be applied to all languages since these languages reflect our existence.

Tilly and Tilly (1998) explain how different degrees of trust affect work contracts and the establishment of networks. Since social networks in general are sets of relations among persons, organisations, communities, or other social units, they add that jobs as roles, bundles of work contracts, durably occupied by human beings, "exist at intersections in those networks" (p. 79). From this perspective, it is reasonable to argue that not developing literacy in indigenous languages and not using these languages in fostering employment opportunities, education, health care, and more humane conditions of life in rural areas leave indigenous people or rural inhabitants jobless for life in a modern world, vulnerable to diseases, poverty, and disparagement by urban inhabitants and industrialised nations of the Global North. This overarching state of being of rural or indigenous people denotes the lack of trust in them and in their capacity, the lack of recognition of their existence. Hence, this nationally and internationally entrenched behaviour since the colonial era is evidence of what I have described above as *an existential discriminatory behaviour*, that is, a behaviour that fails or resists to recognise the rights of all languages, rurality, urbanity, and many other significant cultural and humane elements as *embedded existential realities of life*.

In the age of industrial and international cooperation, one wonders how the professed notion of solidarity has been applied to rural communities in the Global South when these communities have not seen national and international investments that demonstrate trust and respect for the right to work for these people. Since their languages are not used or recognised by national and international language politics, how can investors of goodwill work and establish relationships with these communities? This is one of the cases where existential sociolinguistics intervenes for the existential justice for all languages and promotes "global intercultural solidarity" (Balosa, 2022c, p. 16). This is also where philosophical reflection plays a critical role in deconstructing discriminatory policies and political discourses. For example:

- How can rural inhabitants survive in the age of global economic and political interconnectedness without the basic conditions of life and without the presence of basic human rights (right to work, healthcare, hygiene, drinking water, electricity, basic literacy in their native languages) in their areas?

- How can investors operate in these areas when the languages of rural communities are not used or not recognised by the rest of the citizens of the country and the rest of the world?
- In cases where national and international lingua francas (English, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Russian, Lingala, Swahili, Kikongo, Afrikaans) are not known or spoken by the rural or indigenous people, in which languages should national or foreign investors communicate with these indigenous people?

These questions should help us understand that all languages are national and universal cultural and economic resources that should be developed and acquired for various purposes if we are to counteract hegemonic ideologies and politics and strive for equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity. Therefore, as mentioned earlier, existential sociolinguistics perceives any language as an *embedded existential reality of life* in the same way one perceives race, gender, rurality, and urbanity. This perception should encourage policymakers to adopt its framework for transparent social cooperation (Gallardo, 2014). It describes linguistic, racial, gender, and environmental discriminatory attitudes, emotions, and actions as *embedded existential discriminatory behaviour* toward vulnerable people, languages, communities, and “cultures in marginalized communities and remote places” (Blewitt, 2008, p. 181). How does existential sociolinguistics foster existential justice? What does existential justice entail? How does existential justice differ from social justice? These questions will be answered in the following section.

2.4. Existential sociolinguistics and existential justice

To answer the above questions, it can be said that existential sociolinguistics fosters existential justice by advocating for the inseparability of the treatment of all languages with the treatment of their speakers or speech communities. It also accomplishes this role by arguing that any discriminatory behaviour toward a language is tantamount to discriminatory behaviour toward the speakers of that language. Furthermore, existential sociolinguistics sustains existential justice by proposing that every language is an *embedded existential reality of life*. In fact, we should critically and radically reject any national and international discriminatory and hegemonic ideologies and politics that violate the rights and the dignity of minority languages. Therefore, the overarching advocacy of existential justice is anchored in the fact that all existing languages deserve the same treatment—the same respect and dignity— since “no language exists in isolation” (Fishman, 1976, p. 150), and the hope of sustainable development of any community is inseparable from the sustainable development of its language (Royce, 1916). For example, in his book *The Hope of the Great Community*, American Philosopher Josiah Royce

(1916) uses a quote from Emmanuel Kant (1724-1804) to remind us of the importance of justice for the welfare of communities: “If justice meets utter wreck (complete destruction), then there is no worth whatever in the continued existence of human life in this world” (p. 27). Indeed, when injustice and inequalities dominate societies, it is difficult for languages and their speakers or their communities to flourish and achieve sustainable development (MacNeill, 2020).

It is also anchored in the fact that “languages and intercultural communication” or intercultural relations are interdependent and that the flourishing of any individual or society depends on this communicative relational capacity (Phipps & Guilherme, 2004, p. 1). National and international laws that violate these principles promote discriminatory hegemonic ideologies and politics and narrow self-interests rather than working for the “common interest” and the notion that “every human being (every language) has the right to equal (equitable) consideration” or the right to *building more humane relationships* (BMHR) (Altman & Wellman, 2009; p. 123; Raftopoulos, 2019). In this regard, it is encouraging to appreciate John Rawls’s notion of “the fair value of the equal political liberties” proposed in his theory of justice (Rawls, 2001, p. 148). Rawls writes: “The fair value of the equal political liberties enables citizens to participate in public life” (p. 148). He adds that:

while citizens’ basic rights and liberties are effectively equal—all have the right to vote, to run for political office and to engage in party politics, and so on—social and economic inequalities in background institutions are ordinarily so large that those with greater wealth and position usually control political life and enact legislation and social policies that advance their interests. (Rawls, 2001, p. 148)

Indeed, the control of political life of languages in multilingual societies has been, and continues to be, under the control of the ‘dominant’ national and international political, corporate, and intellectual elites. I expect to see these elites understand that inequalities cannot bring an overarching happiness for a human society and sooner or later may ruin the entire society. Thus, existential justice for language policies in multilingual societies should reflect this understanding and should lead the present political and intellectual elites to adjust their mindsets and adopt more humane language policies for better existence for all—happiness for all (Collins, 1999[2018]; Craig et al., 2008). This argument supports the idea that “language does not develop independently of the activity of socially organized individuals, but reflects, dialectically, that activity, and all of its twists and turns as it develops historically” (Collins, 1999[2018], p. 256). For every language to receive the treatment it deserves and play a significant role within the wider network of

social relations, policymakers must transcend their narrow self-interest-centred mindset and implement equitable, inclusive, and dignifying language policies that honour all languages in multilingual societies (Edwards, 2012).

2.5. Existential justice

In this section, the question ‘what does existential justice entail?’ will be answered. In his book *Revolution, Reform, & Social Justice: Studies in the Theory and Practice of Marxism*, the American philosopher Sidney Hook (1975) argues that “[h]appiness in a human society must have a proper foundation in justice” (p. 124). It seemed to him that John Adams (1797-1801), the second president of the United States, meant this understanding of the relationship between justice and happiness in a human society when he wrote: “As the happiness of the people is the sole end of government, so the consent of the people is the only foundation of it” (Hook, 1975, p. 124). I find this statement encouraging and meaningful in supporting the idea of existential justice as a comprehensive justice for happiness for all. This model of justice should sustain comprehensive planning and policies, attitudes, and actions that generate social “cooperation”, security, happiness, and mutual empowerment (Dworkin, 2006, p. 32; Piller, 2016; Rawls, 2001).

Balosa (2022b, p. 7289) defines existential justice as:

. . . the understanding that as human beings, beyond our cultural, racial, class, gender, sexuality, and age difference, we are all endowed with unalienable rights and dignity and that we all, along with our distinct environments, deserve to be treated with the absolute respect and recognition. Therefore, no human being deserves less respect than another human being.

From this perspective, existential justice fosters the notion of inseparability of the treatment of languages from the treatment of human beings as advocated by existential sociolinguistics in that no language, nor any human being, should deserve more respect and more rights than another. I am not suggesting that there should not be equitable honour and status according to sociocultural and political-moral consensus of particular society or community, rather I am arguing against the pre-existing hierarchical, status-based order of the application of justice based on privileged versus non-privileged human beings, languages, cultures, gender, ages, classes, communities, institutions, nations, and continents (Fishman, 1976; Marcel, 1954). That is, existential justice critically and radically opposes a manipulative model of justice established by the powerful and dominant political, corporate, and intellectual elites to sustain their discriminatory ideologies, business, and politics intended to maintain the status quo and their control of the world. This “existential

injustice” (Balosa, 2022c, p. 21) has generated alienation in people who have been colonised or are being neo-colonised today and must be rejected (cf. Wellman & Simmons, 2005). Both national and international laws that discriminate against certain groups of human beings, languages, and cultures must also be resisted.

2.6. Existential justice versus social justice

To understand the difference between existential justice and social justice, this section explains the ways social justice is both defined and criticized (Craig et al., 2008; Kluegel et al., 1995; Novak & Adams, 2015). Piller (2016, p. 5) defines social justice as “[a] goal and process of enabling the equal participation of all groups and the equitable distribution of resources in society to empower communities to create a more equitable and socially just world.” She criticises the work of social justice research for rarely addressing language issues. Piller argues:

On the map of contemporary social justice engagement with social justice, social justice research principally focusses on disadvantage and discrimination related to gender, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, religion, and age—it is extremely rare for language to feature as a basis on which individuals, communities, or nations may be excluded.

Adopting her social justice perspective from philosopher Nancy Fraser, Piller (2016, p. 5) explains that she conceives of social justice as “constituted along three dimensions, namely, economic redistribution, cultural recognition, and political representation.” From these three dimensions, Piller (2016) explores the relationship between linguistic diversity and economic inequality, the relationship between linguistic diversity and cultural domination, and the relationship between linguistic diversity and imparity of political participation. Briar-Lawson et al. (2011) support these perspectives and explain that “social justice advocates must address the human costs of exclusionary dynamics, which create disparities in access to basic resources for survival.” They add:

A social justice perspective on globalization assumes that change for human and environmental betterment is not only possible but also urgently compelling—as we sign on as change agents, we embrace beliefs that people, communities, institutions, and nations can change and that human service practice can change. We do not see unnecessary death, starvation, social exclusion, abject poverty, and ethnic hatred or cleansing as inevitable but instead as challenges to larger human rights and social justice agendas, which compel study and informed actions. (p. 4)

Linguistic diversity-based injustice (Piller 2016) can be a barrier to the participation of groups in the sociopolitical life of society, while the inequitable distribution of cultural and linguistic resources in society can seriously hamper social happiness. Finally, this injustice challenges the applicability of human rights and social justice agendas. To solve this situation, social justice agendas need to be involved in overarching justice strategies—existential justice to cover the culture of human dignity in their analysis of the ultimate goals and processes of justice. This strategy, in my opinion, may foster learning from different cultures and languages to generate “planning” for intercultural adjustment (Bratman, 2018, p. 1) to ensure happiness for all.

Talking about the fuzziness and warmth of social justice, Novak and Adams (2015) argue that “social justice is one of the terms most often used in ethical and political discourse, but one will search in vain for definitions of it. Because of its fuzziness and warmth, everybody wants to share in it.” (p. 15). They argue:

[T]here is a whole band of Catholics calling themselves ‘social justice Catholics’, but they rarely give you a forthright definition of social justice, or an explanation of how their view differs from other views of social justice that are widely held. (p. 15)

In their volume *Social Justice and Public Policy: Seeking Fairness in Diverse Societies*, social justice scholar Gary Craig et al. (2008) argue in the same vein in terms of the vagueness of the notion of social justice. For example, they write: “Everybody is in favor of social justice, almost by definition, but what they mean by social justice, the priority they accord to it relative to other objectives, and the public policies they believe follow from it, vary widely” (Craig et al., 2008, p. 1). They insist that political parties, national and international organisations, and governments advocate social justice for their own terms or to promote their own agendas rather than the agenda of equitable redistribution of resources and the treatment of citizens. Unfortunately, in reality, “neither the quality of employment, nor aspects of inclusion other than being part of the process of production, are considered” (Craig et al., 2008, p. 2). They go further arguing that the same applies to international organisations. They write: “Internationally, too, the rhetoric of social justice and tempering the pursuit of economic growth with concern for the less fortunate has gained ground.” The Millennium Declaration of the United Nations affirms

... to have a collective responsibility to uphold the principles of human dignity, equality and equity at the global level and to establish a just and lasting peace all over the world, yet the failure to advance social justice

according to any reasonable criteria—the benefit of the least well-off has been noticeable” (Craig et al., 2008, pp. 2-3).

The authors observe:

[T]here is an urgent need to be more explicit in political debate, nationally and internationally, about the different conceptions of social justice being employed, to identify the tensions between them, and provide a sharper analysis of the demands of justice, however conceived. (Craig et al., 2008, p. 3)

Finally, in their volume *Toward What Justice? Describing Diverse Dreams of Justice in Education*, scholars of Critical Race and Indigenous Studies and Ethnic Studies, Eve Tuck and K. Wayne Yang (2018) discuss “a warm ambivalence about the term social justice” (Tuck & Yang, 2018, p. 3). They write:

Perhaps because it is a term not always treated with respect in the academy, social justice is used frequently but rarely defined. Social justice is now commonly associated with many aspects of fields of education, reflected in the titles of conferences, book series, journals, and academic departments. At the same time, at least one major educational research association and its journals maintain distance from the term, citing the need to remain objective or neutral to remain inclusive of all potential members and readers. (Tuck & Yang, 2018, pp. 3, 4)

It is interesting to note that social justice is specifically being applied in the context of the educational field. In this regard, Tuck and Yang (2018) insist:

We want to talk about social justice as words that work as a signal in the field of education, but also in other fields such law, and social science fields. In the interdisciplinary field of education, social justice is a way to signal to ourselves and to one another this epistemological and political difference. Social justice is a way to mark a distinction from the origins and habits of almost all disciplines which emerged in the 19th and 20th centuries and are rooted in colonialism and white supremacy. Social justice education is a way to refer to all research and practice within the domains of education which are a departure from behavioral or cognitive or developmental approaches. This is, of course, not to say that individuals who locate their work in these disciplines do not care about improving the lives of everyday people, but that social justice education has been a way for those outside of those disciplines to still find a home in education and schools of education It is a self-consciousness exception to the otherwise

teleological imperatives of what has, up until now, typified the field(s) of education. It is a *choice away* from pathology and linearity. (Tuck & Yang, 2018, pp. 4-5).

My critique with respect to social justice within all its orientations is that it serves certain needs not the comprehensive existential need of human beings, cultures, languages, and environment. Power relations can affect people and societies if justice at these levels is not clear or established (Royce, 1916). Social justice also needs to address issues related to self-conscience, independence, participation, and sustainable transformational intercultural leadership (Marcel, 1954). How can we expect any change when the powerful leaders of the world responsible for social inequalities are not reminded that their model of leadership and their inclination to injustice and marginalisation of 'the other' are an existential threat to the common humanity? This is where I stand for existential justice because it is a macro justice capable of tackling any injustice and every concern, while also calling for self-scrutiny or for self-consciousness (Grusky & Hill, 2018; Sen, 1995).

2.7. Multilingual societies

Multilingual societies are societies where two or more languages are spoken. In today's globalizing and multilingual world, "linguistic practices come to constitute a terrain for competition, a point of negotiation, a market-place where some practices are valued more highly than others and the value of certain practices changes in the new political economy" (Blackledge & Creese, 2010, p. 215). In a world that is multipolar and intercultural, it is important to understand that the more indigenous or rural languages are treated as languages of low value, the more difficult it becomes for these languages and their communities to participate in the process of sustainable development (Guilherme, 2002, p. 132; MacNeill, 2020; Pieterse, 2018; Rösen, 2021). For example, Pieterse (2018) writes: "To be effective and sustainable, social reforms should be part of the overall growth model and engage macroeconomic imbalances. They should include structural reforms: land reform, fiscal reform, wealth tax, public services, and social investments for the majority" (pp. 102-103). From this perspective, the oppression of minority or indigenous languages can be described as a public services' failure and "global imbalance embedded in domestic imbalances" and lack of domestic reforms (Pieterse, 2018, p. 114). This failure is counterproductive to projects of sustainable development.

Sociolinguist Peter Trudgill (2003) defines multilingualism as "the opposite of monolingualism—a sociolinguistic situation in which more than one language is involved, usually involving also language contact and individual bilingualism" (p. 90). He explains that "many sociolinguists use the term

bilingual to refer to individuals, even if they are trilingual, quadrilingual etc. and reserve the term multilingualism for nations or societies, even if only two languages are involved” (Trudgill, 2003, p. 90; see also Richards & Schmidt, 2013).

Multilingual societies can be problematic societies when language issues are not dealt with equitably and wisely. Serious conflicts, even genocide may occur when hatred and domination among different linguistic groups become stronger. In their book *Multilingualism: A Critical Perspective*, applied linguists Adrian Blackledge and Angela Creese (2010) explain why we should pay attention to critical perspectives on multilingualism. They argue that the reason is that “public discourses and language policies across the world, especially in the developed, English-speaking world, are frequently out of step with the plural linguistic practices of its population” (Blackledge & Creese, 2010, p. 4). For example, they mention that:

more than 300 languages and varieties are spoken on a daily basis in England. However, in recent times, the discourse of public elites has proposed that minority languages other than English are associated with, and even responsible for, problems in society. (Blackledge & Creese, 2010, p. 5)

In colonised multilingual societies, the choice of language use affects even family interaction. For example, in their book *Linguistic Human Rights and Language Policy in the Kenyan Education System*, discussing language attitudes, Sure and Ogechi (2009, p. 168) report that:

... the use of mother tongue in the family is still prevalent although it is used more with parents than with siblings. The use of English at home also reflects the unequal access to education between gender groups, i.e., more fathers than mothers speak English. The family domain is already being invaded by non-mother languages.

Another observation about language and family comes from Florian Coulmas (2018) who, in his book, *An Introduction to Multilingualism: Language in a Changing World*, points out that “How children experience their multilinguality is strongly influenced by the society in which they grow up and by its ideology, which may include factors that lead to the valorization of languages” (p. 97). In this regard, the work of sociolinguist and educational linguist Nancy H. Hornberger (2011), *Can Schools Save Indigenous Languages? Policy and Practice on Four Continents*, appeals to recognise that schools alone are not enough to do the job and that:

... indigenous language revitalization always occurs within an ecology of languages, in a context of other local and global languages with their relative statuses and uses in domains and social fields such as employment, religion, government, cultural life, media, and others. (p. 1)

Hornberger (2011) insists that “indigenous language revitalization is subject to the vagaries of policy, politics, and power; and it is subject to the economics of the linguistic marketplace” (Hornberger, 2011; see also Mowbray, 2012; Said, 1995). Here again, existential justice can provide guidance for equitable, inclusive, and dignifying language policies within multilingual societies by implementing policies that encourage attitudes and actions of mutual respect, dignity, and equal linguistic political-legal power for all languages (Grusky & Hill, 2018).

2.8. Econotechnocracy and existential justice

In his book *Life in a Technocracy: What It Might Be Like*, the American writer Harold Loeb (1933[1996]) discusses “the mysticism of money” and the way it resembles to a religion (p. 27). Loeb writes that we live in a system where “Owing to the lack of a better name this integrated belief system shall be called the Mysticism of Money” (p. 27). He explains:

Money, because money is the measuring staff of values and its accumulation has become the object of those efforts conventionally accepted as proper; mystic, because the validity of the money standard and the intrinsic merit of money making are accepted on faith. The average person would no more question the desirability of amassing a fortune, even though the needs with money can fill were already satisfied, than he would question the truth of a mathematical sum. Thus, the Mysticism of Money resembles a religion in that it is unnecessary to defend its assumptions by reason. (p. 27)

Loeb’s observation helps understand why, in my opinion, language attitudes today are also influenced by the Mysticism of Money. Languages with economic and technologic power (writing literacy, computer literacy, and academic prominence) are to be favoured in the political-economic, sociocultural, and environmental public spaces to rural or indigenous languages.

Another insightful resource is the book *Technocracy* written by the French political scientist Jean Meynaud (1969). He writes:

Technocracy is a system where the political point of view is subordinate to that of production and the very nature of this knowledge has changed

from the wisdom of Greek philosophers to the art of using electronic computers and interpreting the results. (pp. 194-195)

Meynaud (1969) explains:

In the broadest sense of the term, technocracy ideology demonstrates the pressure of technology on political system; from this point of view, it seems legitimate to connect its birth with the first Industrial Revolution, which, in essence, was precisely of a politico-technical nature. But if technocracy is given a relative sense, that is, if it is the function of the state in the direction of existing techniques, its existence may be traced back to a much earlier period. For example, Plato's 'sophocratic' ideal permeated by technical element, since his ideal expresses the wish that philosophers should be kings or kings should be philosophers (p. 194).

Here again, we can understand why languages without or with less power to influence industrial realisation and technology are excluded from the current world. From Harold Leob and Jean Meynaud and my personal experience, I have decided to use rather econotechnocracy as a comprehensive term to describe today's world order or system dominated by the 'Mysticism of Money', military power, and technology information (Balosa, 2022c). While there are many concepts of justice, the need for a model of justice that is comprehensive—existential justice—is more crucial than ever if we are to strive for "the humane agenda" or more inclusive policies to give the culture of human dignity a position superior to the culture of econotechnocracy (Fanon, 1952[2008], p. 8; Galbraith, 1996; Said, 1995).

Econotechnocracy is defined as "the theory of world order anchored on economic and technological power, order in which merely those with economic and technological power are counted as true partners in the circle of world leadership and in the culture of human dignity" (Balosa, 2022c, p. 16; Friedman, 2019). That is, the economic, military, information technology, infrastructure, and corporate dominance of the world is used as a ground for control over the rest of the world rather than the rule of law, the human rights, and human dignity. While the economical-political and technological power has the ability to foster justice, equity, and human dignity for all, it lacks the will, the generosity, the genuine democratic personality to act positively for the common good (Lasswell, 1976). From this perspective, language, culture, human groups, communities, and nations without economic, military, and high information technological power are not treated equally or are not qualified to transparent international political-economic relations.

In the case of minority languages in multilingual societies, these languages are naturally perceived as non-existent both by the national and international elites. For example, Edward Said (1995) discusses the way in which Indian languages were portrayed by the British Colonial Power and the way in which Indian elites being educated in England were taught about their languages as languages not worth of literary work, inferior to English, and not worth of providing opportunities for economic and intellectual prosperity. Said (1995, p. 92) writes:

All writers, intellectuals, and citizens necessarily confront the question of how as people living and working in one culture they relate to other cultures. Never has this been more of a challenge than during the past-imperial period when the rise of nationalism has stimulated a more acute sense of ethnic difference and particularity. So long as England ruled India, for instance, the native elites in Delhi and Calcutta who were educated in British schools were taught that the English language, European culture, and the white race were inherently superior to anything that the Orient might produce by way of languages, cultures, or human species. For several generations Indians were trained to accept that these observations were literally true, and consequently, that their own traditions and languages were inferior and not worthy of study. The rise of anti-imperialist nationalism in India reversed these notions, stressing the primacy of native Indian values and of the various languages that were considered to be the product of the Indian mind.

In today's postcolonial era, language policies in multilingual societies continue to display this colonial mentality. Neocolonial political and intellectual elites demonstrate bias and discriminatory attitudes and actions towards minority languages. These elites favour language policies centred on the dominant languages related to economic and political self-interest establishment rather than linguistic justice and dignity for all (Fanon, 1952[2008]; 1963[2004]).

Econotechnocracy affects not merely language choice and national and international relations, it also affects human relationships, friendships, and families. For example, the Bible (in Proverbs 19: 4-7) says: "Wealth makes many friends; But the poor is separated from his neighbor." Therefore, a wealthy person or a language that provides economic and technological power attracts institutional and governmental policies and more individuals than indigenous languages. This is where existential justice intervenes. Instead of using economic and technological power as the only factor to empower all languages and speech communities including rural and urban communities, existential justice uses the factor of existential recognition. That is, as long as a language or a community exists, it deserves more humane attention and

dignified treatment. In an interconnected world, discriminatory treatment of minority languages and their communities affects the overarching development and prosperity of the international community (Dworkin, 2006).

3. Method

This study uses philosophical reflection as its research method. The entire world is a multilingual society. Therefore, addressing existential injustice for language policies in multilingual societies entails reflecting on the motives that sustain discourses that reject inclusive and dignifying language policies for the common good. If there are national and international laws that regulate the rights and dignity of all languages and their rights to flourish and to be used in public and political spaces, why do these laws not work in reality? Philosophical reflection as a research method fosters a radical critical humanist reflection anchored in equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity to decolonise mindsets entrenched in power relations, oppression, and exclusion (Wa Thiong'o, 1986). Marcel (1963) uses philosophical reflection to foster a true unity, to foster universal symbolic brotherhood. He writes: "The problem of human beings considered in the anguished context of today's world requires a conscientious reflection; reflection I consider to be essential the relationship between philosophical research and life" (pp. 3, 4, 13; cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a).

In agreement with Marcel (1963), philosophical reflection as a research method for investigating the role of existential justice in multilingual societies is a choice that may characterise one as an agent of change for equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity (EDIHD). That is an agent of existential justice and happiness for all. This position supports the understanding of language issues as social issues and it is difficult to engage in BMHR without paying attention to language. Coulmas (2018) reminds us that "language is quintessentially social. Wherever we use it we interact with others, regardless of how many languages are involved in the process" (p. 96). For this reason, using philosophical reflection as a research method in this study encourages us to reflect on social issues including language issues affecting us as human beings—social beings (Marcel, 1963; Moreno Cabrera, 2016).

4. General discussion

Drawing upon the affordances, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), of philosophical reflection as a research method, this paper argues that existential sociolinguistics fosters existential justice in *building more humane relations* among languages and communities within multilingual societies by (a) promoting unity within diversity and (b) by regulating our mindset to promote intercultural adjustment and build more humane relationships. This implies

that multilingual societies are, by way of analogy, like a physical house where each language should be considered as a wall among other walls of that house. Imagine a house that loses one of its walls! That house may fall apart. It is in this sense that existential sociolinguistics fosters existential justice in multilingual societies. Therefore, the idea of dealing with linguistic diversity entails displaying a mindset committed to attitudes and actions that sustain the peaceable and prosperous development of “humanity, order, unity, security, and equity (HOUSE)” (Balosa, 2022b, p. 7296). If all languages as national and universal cultural resources can be managed within this mindset, they can help citizens or speakers of these languages and their communities participate in this process (Galbraith, 1996). This should encourage scholars and students in social sciences, humanities, and related fields to critically and radically resist econotechnocracy—a world system where economic and technological power is the centre of policies rather than justice and human dignity for more humane national and international relations, legislations, and alliances (Mowbray, 2012).

This study has found that multilingual policies and legislations across global institutions such as the United Nations (UN), the African Union (AU), the European Union (EU), and the majority of multilingual nations are “struggling” (Hult, 2023, p. 52) to implement multilingual policies anchored to equity, diversity, inclusion, and human dignity. The model of multilingualism in place encourages and advocates for multilingualism merely for business and market purposes. Unfortunately, this model of multilingualism is reluctant to foster what I call *global intercultural solidarity*, that is, a treatment of all languages and their speakers as worth of equal rights and dignity including the right to position of power control. This treatment prevents minority languages and their speakers from having access to “needed information and training” that should prepare them in actively participating in the democratic and sociocultural development of national and international projects (Hult, 2023, p. 54; Tonkin, 2023). This is where existential justice, with the support of existential sociolinguistics can make the difference—the fostering of *linguistic global intercultural solidarity*, that is, the equitable and dignifying treatment of all languages and their speakers independently of their economic and technological power.

5. Conclusion

This study has discussed existential sociolinguistics and the way it fosters the theory of existential justice. It has explained the difference between existential justice and social justice and argued that social justice is a component of existential justice. It has also discussed the ongoing debate about social justice and how disciplines, governments, political parties, and institutions use social justice to advance their own agendas. Scholars who identify themselves as non-

ideological users of social justice define social justice as the habit of heart to address the need of individuals and community rather than the advancing of the interest of large governments (Novak & Adams, 2015). Looking also at linguistic diversity (Piller, 2016) and making connection between social justice education and the widely spread notion of social justice (Tuck & Yang, 2018) has informed us about why existential justice matters.

In addition, research on how non-mother languages have invaded families of countries that were colonised (the case of Kenya) (Sure & Ogechi, 2009), and the accusation of political and intellectual elites of minority language speakers as the cause of social and cultural problems and other countries in UK (Blackledge & Creese, 2010) has also demonstrated the limitation of social justice. Furthermore, research has also informed us that the process of revitalization of minority languages is not the problem of merely the schools, rather it is “an ecology of practices” (Hornberger, 2011, p. 1). After all, Hult (2023) mentions how multinational organizations including the United Nations struggle “with implementation of their multilingual aspirations and ideas” (p. 52). It can therefore be concluded, in my opinion, that the struggle for linguistic justice in national and international laws and language policy is a struggle for human dignity for all. Therefore, existential justice helps overcome the abstract use of various terms related to justice including social justice. I hope that existential justice as a macro justice (Kluegel et al., 1995) fosters intercultural communication justice in this intercultural world. My points lend support to John Rawls’ (1979, p. 6) discussing of a well-ordered society, where he writes, “When fully articulated, any conception of justice expresses a conception of the person, of the relations between persons, and of the general structure and ends of social cooperation.”

In sum, an important ‘washback’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of this paper is that adopting existential justice in addressing issues of minority languages in multilingual societies should foster the culture of human dignity and the skill for sustainable development for all. In an Econotechnocracy—a world order where economic and technological powers subordinate justice and human dignity and sustain humiliating treatment towards “the public” (Nagel, 1978, p. 75)—there is a need to cooperate to promote justice for multilingualism. In this context, existential justice may help defenders of linguistic rights and dignity foster attitudes and actions in support of *linguistic intercultural solidarity* for the common good.

Notes:

1. For more detailed discussion of equity and other related topics, see Huang (2024), Kruger-Marais (2024), Motaung (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), and Salmani Nodoushan (2024).

The Author

Dr David Balosa (dbalosa1@umbc.edu) is a high school teacher in the school district of Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, in the United States where he teaches philosophy, French, and Spanish and is a member of the School equity, diversity, and inclusion team. Dr Balosa has taught undergraduate and graduate courses on World languages, sociolinguistics, and intercultural communication at LaSalle University, Pennsylvania State University/Abington, Delaware University, and Arcadia University. His research interests include: sociolinguistics; intercultural communication; political/critical discourse analysis; postcolonial studies; Lusophone studies; African literature; and social, moral, legal, and political philosophy.

References

- Allen, B. J. (2011). *Difference matters: Communicating social identity* (2nd ed.). Waveland Press.
- Altman, A., & Wellman, C. H. (2009). *A liberal theory of international justice*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199564415.001.0001>
- Anderson, S. R. (2012). *Languages: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780199590599.001.0001>
- Balosa, D. (2022a). Existential sociolinguistics: The fundamentals of the political legitimacy of linguistic minority rights. In S. Makoni, C. G. Severo, A. Abdelhay & A. Kaiper-Marquez (Eds.), *The languaging of higher education in the global south: De-colonizing the language of scholarship and pedagogy* (pp. 147-162). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003138433>
- Balosa, D. (2022b). "Integrationism: Roy Harris artspeak, artistic creativity, and human diversity in the age of globalization. *Journal Forum Lingüístico*, 19(2), 7280-7298. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5007/1984-8412.2022.e84042>
- Balosa, D. (2022c). The relationship between Portuguese and indigenous languages in the community of Portuguese language countries: An existential sociolinguistics perspective. *Journal Conjuntura Austral*, 13(63), 13-28. <https://doi.org/10.22456/2178-8839.123331>

- Blackledge, A., & Creese, A. (2010). *Multilingualism: A critical perspective*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0047404511000285>
- Bratman, M. E. (2018). *Planning, time, and self-governance: Essays in practical rationality*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190867850.001.0001>
- Briar-Lawson, K., Roth, W., Bonpane III, B., Onetti-Bischoff, M. C., & Roth, D. (2011). Globalization: Setting the stage for a social justice agenda. In W. Roth & K. Briar-Lawson (Eds.), *Globalization, social justice, and the helping professions* (pp. 3-23). State University of New York Press.
- Chaka, C. (2024). Multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and activism: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 7-28.
- Collins, C. (1999[2018]). *Language, ideology and social consciousness: Developing a sociohistorical approach*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429026768>
- Coulmas, F. (2018). *An introduction to multilingualism: Language in a changing world*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12437>
- Craig, G., Burchardt, T., & Gordon, D. (Eds.). (2008). *Social justice and public policy: Seeking fairness in diverse societies*. Policy Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt9qgvs3.19>
- Danesi, M. (2020). *Language, society, and new media: Sociolinguistics today* (3rd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003029427-1>
- Dworkin, R. (1978). *Taking rights seriously*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3479972>
- Dworkin, R. (2006). *Is democracy possible here? Principles for a new political debate*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400827275>
- Edwards, J. (2012). *Multilingualism: Understanding linguistic diversity*. <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.50-1302>
- Edwards, J. (2013). *Sociolinguistics: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780199858613.001.0001>

- Fanon, F. (1952/2008). *Black skin, white masks* (R. Philcox, Trans.). Grove Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1vwmfcj.5>
- Fanon, F. (1963/2004). *The wretched of the earth* (R. Philcox, Trans.). Grove Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198717133.013.54>
- Fishman, J. A. (1976). *Bilingual education: An international sociological perspective*. Newbury House Publisher. <https://doi.org/10.2307/412845>
- Fishman, J. A. (1989). *Language and ethnicity in minority sociolinguistic perspective*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781800418066>
- Friedman, J. (2019). *Power without knowledge: A critique of technocracy*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190877170.001.0001>
- Galbraith, J. K. (1996). *The good society: The humane agenda*. Houghton Mifflin Company. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.313.7063.1016>
- Gallardo, M. E. (Ed.). (2014). *Developing cultural humanity: Embracing race, privilege and power*. Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483388076>
- Grusky, D. B., & Hill, J. (2018). *Inequality in the 21st century: A reader*. Westview Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429499821-1>
- Guilherme, M. (2002). *Critical citizens for an intercultural world: Foreign language education as cultural politics*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781853596117>
- Hook, S. (1975). *Revolution, reform, and social justice: studies in the theory and practice of Marxism*. New York University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00213624.1977.11503494>
- Hornberger, N. H. (Ed.). (2011). *Can schools save indigenous languages? Policy and practice on four continents*. Palgrave MacMillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230582491_1
- Huang, Y.-W. (2024). Language loss and translingual identities near the Navajo land. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 113-128.

- Hult, F. M. (2023). Sustainable multilingual education. In L. McEntee-Atalianis & H. Tonkin (Eds.), *Language and sustainable development* (pp. 51-78). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-24918-1_4
- Kluegel, J. R., Csepeli, G., Kolosi, T., Örkény, A., & Neményi, M. (1995). Accounting for the rich and the poor: Existential justice in comparative perspective. In J. R., Kluegel, D. S. Mason & B. Wegener (Eds.), *Social justice and political change: Public opinion in capitalist and post-communist states* (pp. 179-207). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110868944.179>
- Kruger-Marais, E. (2024). Subtitling for language acquisition: Eye tracking as predictor of attention allocation in education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 129-150.
- Lasswell, H. D. (1976). *Power & personality*. The Norton Library. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315127149>
- Loeb, H. (1933[1996]). *Life in a technocracy: What it might be like*. Syracuse University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3107009>
- MacNeill, T. (2020). *Indigenous cultures and sustainable development in Latin America*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37023-7>
- Mapuya, M. (2024). Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies: Promoting social justice in accounting education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 131-155.
- Marcel, G. (1954). *The decline of wisdom*. The Harvill Press. <https://doi.org/10.1086/484741>
- Marcel, G. (1963). *The existential background of human dignity*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674865068>
- Meynaud, J. (1969). *Technocracy* (P. Barnes, Trans.). The Free Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0003055400129454>
- Moreno Cabrera, J. C. (2016). *La dignidad e igualdad de las lenguas: Crítica de la discriminación lingüística* (2nd ed.). Alianza editorial. <https://doi.org/10.17979/rgf.2000.1.0.5411>

- Motaung, L. B. (2024). Translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial programme at a South African university. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 81-104.
- Mowbray, J. (2012). *Linguistic justice: international law and language policy*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199646616.001.0001>
- Nagel, T. (1978). Ruthlessness in public life. In S. Hampshire (Ed.), *Public and private morality*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511625329.005>
- Ndlangamandla, S. C. (2024). The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 105-130.
- Ndlangamandla, S. C., Chaka C., Shange, T., & Shandu-Phetla, T. (2024). COVID-19 crosslinguistic and multimodal public health communication strategies: social justice or emergency political strategy? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 7-34.
- Nkhi, S. E., & Shange, T. (2024). The impact of pedagogical translanguaging in enhancing communicative competence of university students in Lesotho. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 29-52.
- Novak, M., & Adams, P. (2015). *Social justice isn't what you think it is*. Encounter Book. <https://doi.org/10.1353/acs.2016.0065>
- Phipps, A., & Guilherme, M. (Eds.). (2004). *Critical pedagogy: Political approaches to language and intercultural communication*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781853597541>
- Pieterse, J. N. (2018). *Multipolar globalization: Emerging economies and development*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315312859>
- Piller, I. (2016). *Linguistic diversity and social justice*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199937240.003.0007>
- Raftopoulos, E. (2019). *International negotiation: A process of relational governance for international common interest*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108164870>

- Rawls, J. (1979). A well-ordered society. In P. Laslett & J. Fishkin (Eds.), *Philosophy, politics, and society* (pp. 6-20). Yale University Press.
- Rawls, J. (2001). *Justice as fairness: A restatement*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139026741.225>
- Richards, J. C., & Schmidt, R. (2013). *Longman dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics* (4th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315833835-22>
- Royce, J. (1916). *The hope of the great community*. The MacMillan. <https://doi.org/10.5422/fordham/9780823224845.003.0016>
- Rüsen, J. (2021). *Humanism: Foundations, diversities, developments*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003170501>
- Rüsen, J., & Laass, H. (Eds.). (2009). *Humanism in intercultural perspective: Experiences and expectations*. Transaction Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839413449>
- Said, E. W. (1995). *Peace and its discontents: Essays on Palestine in the Middle East peace process*. Vintage Books. <https://doi.org/10.1525/jps.1996.26.1.00p00854>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021a). Language and socialization? It is all about sociosemiotics. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 15(2), 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.4396/2021207>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021b). Test affordances or test function? Did we get Messick's message right? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 127-140. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514614>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021c). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884. <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v8i3.21406>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2022). Breaking out of the Gricean vicious cycle: Let's divorce semantics and just agree that there is no meaning in language. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(3), 33-60. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514602>

- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2024). Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 63-90.
- Sen, A. (1995). *Inequality reexamined*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0198289286.001.0001>
- Sen, A. (1999). *Commodities and capabilities*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2232999>
- Sure, K., & Ogechi, N. O. (2009). *Linguistic human rights and language policy in the Kenyan education system*. OSSREA. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10228195.2011.625038>
- Tilly, C. (2005). *Trust and rule*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511618185>
- Tilly, C., & Tarrow, S. (2015). *Contentious politics* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199566020.003.0019>
- Tilly, C., & Tilly, C. (1998). *Work under capitalism*. Westview. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429268151>
- Tonkin, H. (2023). Introduction: Diversity of language, unity of purpose. In L. J. McEntee-Atalianis & H. Tonkin (Eds.), *Language and sustainable development* (pp.1-10). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-24918-1_1
- Trudgill, P. (2003). *A glossary of sociolinguistics*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781474473323>
- Tuck, E., & Yang, K. W. (Eds.). (2018). *Toward what justice? Describing diverse dreams of justice in education*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351240932>
- Wa Thiong'o, N. (1986). *Decolonizing the mind: The politics of language in African literature*. East African Educational Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.2307/524049>
- Wellman, C. H., & Simons, A. J. (2005). *Is there a duty to obey the law?* Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511809286>

Williams, R. (1977). *Marxism and literature*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/08992363-8090166>

Xu, Y., & Fang, F. (2024). Promoting educational equity: The implementation of translanguaging pedagogy in English language education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 53-80.